

**Maps produced in the process of application of
CSA and NVZ designation methodologies**

Legend

P Index values

- <3
- 3 - 13
- 13 - 18
- 18 - 23
- 23 - 28
- 28 - 36
- River Kruostas

Map attached to Lithuanian coordinate system (LKS-94).
Open street map is used as basemap.

INSPIRING
ENVIRONMENT

Figure 1. P Index value in the selected subcatchment of Nevėžis catchment.

Figure 2. Critical source areas of N losses and potential risk areas.

Figure 3. NSAs and potential NSAs identified based on the monitoring data.

Figure 4. NSAs and potential NSAs identified based on the modelling data.

Figure 5. NSAs and potential NSAs identified based on the combination of monitoring and modelling data.